

ANALYSIS OF THE SYSTEM OF GRANTING ACADEMIC AND FINANCIAL INDEPENDENCE TO FOREIGN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: In this article, Canadian higher education institutions are given broad autonomy to solve some issues related to the financial sphere, and financial autonomy is covered.

Keywords: Canadian liberal model, HEIs, Board of Trustees, Board secretary, registrar, treasurer, professors, associate professors, lecturers, instructor.

Introduction

Today, the Canadian liberal model is widely used in the administration of higher education institutions in many countries. This model is favored by most developed countries in terms of the degree of autonomy it implies. This model was formed and improved in Canada, and in order to know its content and effectiveness, it would be appropriate to research the possibilities of management of higher education institutions in these countries. Higher education institutions in Canada do not have a single centralized management system. Although the traditions of freedom and financial independence are clearly manifested in the management of non-governmental organizations, they are distinguished by the presence of different and unique aspects. In most of the higher education institutions of these countries, a wide autonomy has been created regarding academic matters. In particular, it is related to the opening and closing of academic programs, determining their content, and controlling the quality of the educational process through internal mechanisms. Also, it can be seen that the financial autonomy of higher education institutions develops much slower than institutional autonomy and academic freedom. Only in the conditions of institutional autonomy, it is obvious that the financial autonomy of TSOs is considered as its integral element. For comparison, the main groups of indicators of financial autonomy of higher educational institutions proposed by scientists in different years are given.

The management autonomy of Canadian higher education institutions is also unique and is recognized as one of the most effective forms of management today. The country has a decentralized education system, and in terms of management of HEIs, Canada's ten provinces are very different from each other. However, there are a number of common characteristics common to all

Canadian higher education institutions. A key common feature of Canadian higher education institutions is their adoption of a corporate governance model. In Canada, there is no body responsible for the education sector at the federal level, and there is no Legislation regulating matters in this field. The activities of HEIs and the entire higher education system are governed by the jurisdiction of Canadian provinces.

The members of the Board of Trustees, elected from among professors and teachers and employees of the Higher Education Institution, hold their positions for a period of three years or until a successor is elected. Eight members of the council, appointed by the Governor of the Province, hold office for three years or until a successor is elected. However, the Governor has the power to remove any appointed member from the Board of Trustees. Two members of the Council, elected from among the students, shall hold office for one year or until their successors are elected. The Rector and President shall be members of the Board of Trustees and shall serve as members of the Board for as long as they hold their respective offices. All elected members of the Board are eligible for re-election, but may not hold office for more than six consecutive years.

– Canadian legislation clearly defines persons who are prohibited from being members of the Board of Trustees of HEIs[1]. The following persons may not be elected or hold the position of a member of the Board of Trustees:

- Members of the Canadian Parliament;
- Members of the Provincial Council (provincial government) and Provincial Legislative Assembly (legislative body in Canadian provinces);
- civil servants working in ministries;
- Civil servants appointed by ministers.

If a member of the Board of Trustees is elected or appointed to one of the positions incompatible with the membership of the Board, his membership in the Board shall be terminated. If there are vacancies in the Board of Trustees, due to the death of one of the members or for other reasons, the Secretary of the Board shall notify the next meeting of the Board of Trustees and indicate this in the minutes of the meeting[2]. The Board of Trustees shall meet as necessary, and meetings shall be held at least once every three months. The decision-making mechanism is formed according to two principles:

Availability of a quorum requiring 51% of the members of the Board of Trustees; Majority principle in voting; if the votes are equal, the proposed proposal is rejected[3].

In Canadian HEIs, Boards of Trustees have broad powers to deal with matters

related to the management of the university, control its assets and distribute its financial resources. The following can be distinguished among the council's powers in the area of organizational autonomy:

Determine the rules of meetings and business of the Board of Trustees;

1. To elect the chairman of the council from among its members;
2. To appoint the secretary of the council and to form its committees to perform the tasks of the council, to determine their powers;
3. Approving the rules for recommending and selecting candidates for the president, deans and other high-ranking positions of the Higher Education Institution with the consent of the Senate;
4. To appoint the President of the Higher Education Institution, to determine all faculty deans, professors, associate professors, senior teachers, teachers, lecturers and other members of the teaching staff and their duties;
5. To review the recommendations of the Senate on the establishment of new faculties and departments with relevant professors and academic subjects;

The recommendations and reports of the Advisory Councils are reviewed and taken into account by the HEI governing bodies. The Board of Trustees is responsible for resolving "competence disputes" between all HEIs. In such cases the decision of the Council shall be final.

The Senate of OTM is an integral part of the corporate governance structure. Initially, representatives of the management of OTM could be members of the Senate. With further changes and general democratization of the system, members of the Senate were elected, including from among the student community.

Under Canadian law, the HEI Senate has the following powers and duties:

- organizing meetings and keeping minutes, including determining the quorum necessary for decision-making, electing the vice-chairman who should preside over the Senate meetings in the absence of the President of the Higher Education Institution;
- to establish committees at will, as well as to transfer part of the powers determined by the Senate with the vote of two-thirds of the members of the Senate to the committees;
- Determination of academic and other qualification criteria for admission to HEIs or individual faculties;
- determining the conditions under which applicants must take the exam; determining the procedure for appointing examiners, conducting examinations and evaluating results;

- Submitting a proposal for review, approval and recommendations to the Board of Trustees on revision of academic subjects and instructions in all faculties and departments of the Higher Education Institution;
- providing and awarding academic degrees (except in the field of theology), including honorary academic degrees and certificates of qualification;
- Making recommendations to the Board of Trustees on the opening or closing of faculties, departments and training courses, allocating scholarships, distinguished scholarships, social scholarships and awards (recommendations must be approved by the Board of Trustees);
- awarding grants, famous scholarships, social scholarships and awards;
- determining the rules for managing the library and its activities;
- Determination of the policy of preservation of cultural and historical objects and collections belonging to the higher education institution and its faculties, departments or other departments;
- Establishing a standing committee that can act on behalf of the Senate on issues referred to it by the Board of Trustees;
- Establishment of relations between HEIs, secondary educational institutions and other educational institutions, as well as defining the rules for changing or canceling them (must be approved by the Board of Trustees);
- Establishment of a standing committee, which is the last appeal instance on educational discipline issues;
- Demanding the formation of advisory committees consisting of faculty requirements and the general public[4].

In Canada, the President of HEIs is the highest executive officer of the educational institution. In most HEIs, the president is appointed by the universities themselves, that is, without the intervention of the authorities.

In Canadian higher education institutions, Boards of Trustees are given broad powers. It is the Boards of Trustees that appoint the president of the HEI, deans of all faculties, librarian, registrar, treasurer, professors, associate professors, senior teachers, lecturers, instructors and other members of the faculty and determine their duties. Also, the Council is responsible for the issues of opening new faculties, departments and closing the existing ones, changing the university curriculum.

The Senate of Canadian higher education institutions includes the chancellor, president, academic vice-president, deans of faculties, chief librarian, faculty members, representatives of the student community and other members. The Senate also has broad powers, including setting academic and other eligibility

criteria for students, and awarding grants, distinguished scholarships, social scholarships and awards.

The President of the Higher Education Institution, appointed by the Board of Trustees, has the following powers: to appoint, promote, or recommend the removal of other employees of the Higher Education Institution, except professors and academic staff; establishment of committees whose activities are necessary and appropriate; publication of the annual report on the activities of the university; In consultation with the relevant standing committee of the Senate, prepare the annual budget of the HEI and submit its draft to the Council for consideration.

The Higher Education Council of Canada includes the Rector, the President, members of the Senate, faculty members, graduates of the Higher Education Institution and other members. may be collected for other additional purposes. Therefore, the vast majority of decisions related to the activities of HEIs are made on a general and equitable basis in the Canadian higher education environment, which indicates that their degree of autonomy is important. however, the structure of the Board of Trustees always provides for a certain balance between the direct representatives of the HEI and the members of the Board appointed by the provincial government.

The academic autonomy of Canadian higher education institutions also has its own characteristics, and it is mainly determined by the ability to determine the criteria for the admission of students, to plan educational programs, to determine the quality control mechanisms of the educational process and other academic aspects. In the country, the responsibility for the education sector rests mainly with the provincial governments and is accordingly governed by provincial legislation[5]. Provinces differ greatly in the way they organize their education systems.

In Canada, HEIs have considerable autonomy in determining selection criteria and enrollment. These tasks are assigned to the Boards of Trustees of Higher Education Institutions. It should be noted that any decision of the Board of Trustees regarding the increase or decrease in the number of incoming students is subject to the approval of the University Senate. Determination of the selection criteria for studentship is carried out at the HEI level. The Senate is responsible for resolving all issues related to the quality and other criteria of the selection of applicants[6].

The issues of opening new faculties or closing existing ones are decided at the HEI level, which shows that Canadian HEIs are given wide autonomy in this area.

The Senate of Higher Education Institutions has the right to develop the recommendations of the Board of Trustees on the formation and closure of faculties, departments, educational programs, as well as the establishment of grants, personal and social scholarships, awards[7]. After the decision to open or close a faculty, department or study program is made, the Senate must send it to the Board of Trustees within 10 days. The decision of the Senate comes into force only after approval and confirmation by the Board of Trustees. Thus, in general, Canadian higher education institutions have a wide autonomy in the field of academic matters, and the influence of public authorities on the activities of higher education institutions remains minimal. Canada does not have a formal government mechanism for higher education accreditation. However, all Canadian universities are members of the Canadian Association of Higher Education Institutions, and membership in itself means that the institution is accredited.

In Canada, questions about the content of educational programs are decided at the HEI level. HEIs may take the initiative to review and determine the list of subjects provided by the faculties. Faculties send their recommendations to the Senate of Higher Education Institutions. The Senate Standing Committee then reviews faculty proposals for the curriculum and submits them to the Senate for consideration[8]. In addition, the Senate can independently initiate the revision of scientific programs in all faculties and departments of the Higher Education Institution. After the Senate approves the project on changing the content of subjects or the curriculum, the project is presented to the Board of Trustees in the form of recommendations[9]. The Board of Trustees takes the final decision on improving the content of the programs and the language of instruction.

In the Canadian higher education system, financial autonomy includes the ability to form a reserve of higher education institutions, to maintain a surplus of state funding, to independently determine tuition fees, to implement funds, to invest the existing funds of the university in financial markets, and to own real estate.

It should be noted that the decision on higher education issues in Canada is mainly the exclusive right of the provincial authorities. At the federal level, there is no body responsible for the field of education and no law regulating matters in this field. The activities of HEIs and the entire higher education system are regulated by the jurisdiction of Canadian provinces.

Thus, while Canadian higher education institutions in general are given broad autonomy to resolve some issues related to the financial sector, other

aspects of financial autonomy are significantly limited. The development and approval of the budget of Canada's HEIs takes place within the internal structure of HEIs. Issues of development of the budget project of higher education institutions are a special right of the President. However, the Board of Trustees approves the budget of the OTM. The Board of Trustees can dispose of the free funds of the OTM and invest them at its discretion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although the American liberal model, which offers a large degree of autonomy to the management process of higher education institutions, has been found to be effective and has a significant impact on the quality of education, it is appropriate to form it in a democratic society and in an environment where freedom of speech is highly valued. Problems with legislation, fair trial and corruption in developing countries limit the possibilities of this model and create new challenges for it. Therefore, it is important to improve autonomy in education, taking into account the possibilities of each country.

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